

Experience of foreign countries in the implementation of prosecutor's control in the field of enforcement proceedings

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes issues such as legislation related to the field of enforcement, its foundations, and the experience of foreign countries in conducting enforcement proceedings. Also, the experience and legislation of developed foreign countries are analyzed in this matter.

Key words: executive case, court decisions, foreign experience, international practice, developed state experience, decisions, executive actions, legal basis, positive result, bailiff, legal requirements.

As we live in Uzbekistan, which recognizes the primacy of universally recognized rules of international law and follows the path of democratic states, it is time to deeply understand the world experience and apply the practices of developed foreign countries. In this way, we think that it is not without benefit to take a model from the world's leading countries in terms of liberating the life of the state and society, creating a mechanism for guaranteeing the rights and freedoms of people and citizens. A greater understanding and study of the innovations in the field of enforcement opens the door to great opportunities for lawyers. In order to reform the laws, it is important to study the experience of some developed foreign countries.

In particular, it is necessary to study in depth the laws of development of countries around the world and to reveal and compare the essence of the system of execution of court documents and documents of other bodies in these countries. Because each country has its own procedures for the execution of court decisions, the bodies that execute court decisions can be named differently and distinguished from others. At the same time, the execution of court decisions in each country takes into account the economic and political situation of the society in that country.

Executive proceedings in the Republic of Kazakhstan are organized on the basis of the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Civil Procedure Code, the Law "On Executive Proceedings and the Status of Bailiffs" and other legal documents. In the Republic

of Kazakhstan, as in the Republic of Uzbekistan, effective prosecutorial control over compliance with laws by bailiffs and other persons in the field of executive proceedings has been established.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the orders of the Prosecutor General of the Republic are as important as the orders of the Prosecutor General in the Republic of Kazakhstan. In particular, regarding the field of executive proceedings, there is the order of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 188, adopted on January 18, 2011, “On the organization of prosecutorial control over the legality of executive proceedings”. According to this order, the main task of authorized prosecutors is to ensure compliance with laws in the exercise of the rights of individuals and legal entities established by the constitution and laws, to protect the interests of the state and society, and to prevent violations of the law that may arise in the field.

The main directions of the prosecutor’s office in ensuring the legality of enforcement proceedings in the Republic of Kazakhstan are:

- control over the observance of the rules for the exercise of the rights and interests of persons in need of protection for health or age reasons who are not able to independently exercise their rights;

- control over the clear and uniform application of executive actions carried out by officials of bodies authorized to execute judicial acts and acts of other bodies;

- control over complaints received about the actions or inaction of officials authorized for enforcement proceedings;

In Belarus, control over the legality of court decisions and compliance with laws in their execution is a separate area of prosecutor's control aimed at checking the legality and validity of all court decisions. The subject of control of the prosecutor's office is a check for the legality of court decisions made from the volumes of the economic, civil and criminal courts, and decisions of the appellate instance of the economic court.

The legal basis of the court decision and prosecutor’s control over their implementation in Belarus is the Constitution of Belarus, the Law “On the Prosecutor’s Office,” the Criminal Procedural, Civil Procedural, Economic Procedural Codes and the Code of Administrative Legal Execution.

The main tasks of the prosecutor’s supervision are:

- ensuring the protection of constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens, the interests of the state and society;

- ensuring legislation and preventing offenses in the economic sphere;

enforcement of laws in the execution of judgments and determinations.

The prosecution authorities, in the process of monitoring compliance with laws in the execution of judicial acts and acts of other bodies, constantly monitor the legality of judicial acts, acts and actions of executive state bodies and officials issued during the executive proceedings. It should be especially noted that, unlike Uzbekistan, in the Law of Belarus “On the Prosecutor’s Office,” control over the execution of judicial acts and acts of other bodies is among the main areas of prosecutor’s control.

In Italy, in accordance with the Law “On the Establishment of the Court,” prosecutors monitor the clear and uniform implementation of laws and protect the interests of the state. At the same time, it organizes prosecutor’s control over the direct and effective execution of court decisions. Prosecutors in Italy are part of the judiciary. However, it has its own hierarchical organizational structure.

Enforcement proceedings are governed by the Italian Civil Procedure Code. According to article 474 of this Code, the grounds for enforcement arise from the moment the writ of execution is submitted for execution. The second section, the second chapter of the CPC are devoted to the issues of forced confiscation, control over compliance with laws in the process of forced confiscation is carried out by the courts. The existing Law “On Enforcement Proceedings” in Italy reflects the norms of legal tradition established in society. The bailiffs have the right to establish the amount of property that can be occupied on the basis of the executive act submitted for execution, and to study the information about the person of the debtor. Bailiffs should not harm the interests of the parties in the course of enforcement proceedings and strictly comply with the existing legislation in the company.

The norms of the prosecutor’s office in France were reflected in the Criminal Procedure Code, adopted in 1958. These norms determine the independent participation of the prosecutor in court. In France, prosecutors are representatives of the executive branch. In the execution of court decisions, prosecutors are of great importance in the process of enforcing laws.

According to legal status, the bailiff combines elements of a person who is an independent civil servant. However, each bailiff is subordinate to the republic’s prosecutors in the course of the practical implementation of enforcement proceedings. Bailiffs are appointed to their posts by order of the French Minister of Justice. When appointing bailiffs, the conclusions of prosecutors of the territorial bodies of the prosecutor’s office are important. The prosecution authorities, along with the control over the execution of judicial acts and acts of other bodies, can assist bailiffs in complex executive processes.

Enforcement proceedings in England are the final stage of the civil process. Control over the execution of court decisions in England is carried out by civil courts. In England, as in the United States, there is no position of prosecutor. There are two types of judicial control in England. The first is judicial control in a supervisory manner, the second is administrative. The main purpose of the control is to control the observance and direct application of material and procedural rights of enforcement bodies. Administrative control is entrusted to the court, the purpose of which is to check the direct, fair and objective execution of court decisions. The jurisdiction of the courts in enforcement proceedings entrusts them with the authority to inspect and supervise the activities of enforcement bodies.

In England, enforcement actions are carried out on the basis of the guidance of the claimant. In this situation, the sheriff or bailiff will be aimed at taking recovery measures. Sheriffs are bailiffs in England. Judicial practice in England has examined that the sheriff is responsible for offences committed by his deputy and each of his subordinates and is responsible in court for their actions. That is why sheriffs provide internal control over the execution of court decisions in order to prevent them from committing offenses by their employees.

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